

Monitoring of the Wrangel Island Population of Lesser Snow Geese

STEVEN M. OLSON,¹ United States Fish and Wildlife Service, Division of Migratory Bird Management, 1211 SE Cardinal Court, Vancouver, Washington 98683, USA

TODD A. SANDERS,¹ United States Fish and Wildlife Service, Division of Migratory Bird Management, 1211 SE Cardinal Court, Vancouver, Washington, USA

20 January 2017

Introduction

Lesser snow geese (*Chen caerulescens caerulescens*) breeding on Wrangel Island, Russia are managed as a distinct population referred to as the Wrangel Island Population of lesser snow geese. This population is a shared resource in that it ranges throughout four countries in Asia and North America and is jointly managed by various government agencies in each country. Wrangel Island snow geese winter primarily in British Columbia, Washington, Oregon, and California, but also some winter in Japan and Mexico. During winter, Wrangel Island snow geese coningle with three populations of white geese that breed in the Arctic of North America including the Western Arctic and Midcontinent populations of lesser snow geese and Ross's geese (*Chen rossii*), and are collectively referred to as white geese. Wrangel Island snow geese are subjected to harvest primarily in the United States and Canada, and to a lesser extent in other parts of the population's range. Cooperative monitoring of Wrangel Island snow geese is necessary to effectively manage this internationally shared resource and ensure population viability and opportunities for consumptive and nonconsumptive uses. This paper briefly summarizes existing cooperative monitoring programs for Wrangel Island snow geese and provides available data summaries to facilitate information exchange and cooperative management of Wrangel Island snow geese.

Breeding Population Surveys

Surveys of Wrangel Island snow geese during the breeding season were initiated in 1969 by Russian scientists, through cooperative Russian and United States government agency efforts, and have been conducted annually for over 40 years. The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service and the Pacific Flyway Council, an organization of the 12 western U.S. state governments responsible for wildlife management, have periodically provided funding and personnel to assist with annual surveys of the breeding population and banding on Wrangel Island since 1988. Parameters measured during the survey include total population size, productivity, and area occupied by the breeding colony (Table 1). In 2016, the total population size on Wrangel Island was estimated at 300,000 snow geese, a 25% increase from the 2015 estimate of 240,000, and was the highest estimate on record (Table 1).

Wintering Population Surveys

Surveys of Wrangel Island snow geese have been conducted on primary wintering areas in California and on the Skagit and Fraser river deltas near the border of Washington and British

¹ E-mail: steven_olson@fws.gov; todd_sanders@fws.gov

Columbia in December since 1979 and 1948, respectively (Table 2). Snow geese wintering on the Skagit and Fraser river deltas are assumed to be from the Wrangel Island population, whereas snow geese wintering in California are assumed to be primarily from the Wrangel Island and Western Arctic populations, and to a lesser extent Ross's geese and snow geese from the Midcontinent population. On the Skagit and Fraser river deltas, counts of snow geese have been made from aerial photographs, but prior to 1987 counts of snow geese were made from ground and aerial observations. In California, counts of white geese are made from ground and aerial observations and the proportion that is Ross's geese is estimated from ground surveys. Surveys in California and on the Skagit and Fraser river deltas also provide an index to population productivity from estimates of the ratio of juvenile to adult geese. Surveys were not conducted in California in 2015 because of logistical issues. The most recent reliable survey occurred in 2014 where a total of 1,199,586 white geese were counted in California and on the Skagit and Fraser river deltas (1,141,579 and 58,007, respectively). Lesser snow goose abundance increased in both primary wintering areas of Wrangel Island snow geese during 1948 to present (Table 2).

Banding

Individually identifiable aluminum leg bands from the U.S. Geological Survey's Bird Banding Laboratory have been used to determine recovery distributions and estimate recovery, harvest, and survival rates of Wrangel Island snow geese. Just over 25,000 snow geese have been banded with leg bands on Wrangel Island since 1988 (Table 3). Prior to 1988, only 1,867 snow geese were banded on Wrangel Island, and this during 1975–1979. Additionally, about 500 Wrangel Island snow geese were banded in winter 2012 and 2013 on the Skagit River Delta to study local movement patterns. Of the snow geese banded on Wrangel Island since 1988, about 3,600 also have been fitted with plastic neck bands to study local movement patterns in certain areas in Washington and California. About 4,000 of the leg-banded geese have been recovered (either shot or found dead, recovered and reported) and about 1,200 have been recaptured during banding operations on Wrangel Island. Most (85%) band recoveries have occurred in the United States, and most of these recoveries have come from the states of Washington (41%), California (35%), and Oregon (20%) (Table 4).

Recaptures of banded geese during banding operations provide evidence of interchange among populations of lesser snow geese. Some snow geese banded on Wrangel Island have been recaptured in the Western Arctic (northern Alaska, Northwest Territories, and Nunavut) and vice versa (Table 5). The direction of interchange among populations appears near equal, especially when recaptures are weighted by the number of snow geese banded in each area (Table 5).

Information on migration routes, timing of migrations, and survival of lesser snow geese was derived mostly from the cooperative International Snow Goose Neck Banding Project coordinated by the Canadian Wildlife Service during the 1980s and 1990s. During this time period, over 5,000 snow geese were banded on Wrangel Island with an aluminum leg band and a plastic neck band and or tarsus band for identification with binoculars or other telescopic equipment. Marked snow geese were resighted in migration and wintering areas through a large-scale cooperative survey effort that produced over 22,000 resightings of marked geese (Table 3). In 2016, 199 Wrangel Island snow geese also received plastic neck bands, and eight geese also received GSM (Global System for Mobile communications; the global digital cellular

telecommunications system) radios to document migration routes and timing of migration of these geese. Currently, resight data is of limited value in determining distribution patterns of snow geese because resightings depend in part on resight effort. There has been no recent coordinated effort to resight neck banded snow geese in western North America. Available resight data comes from localized studies to evaluate bird distribution and habitat use.

Harvest Surveys

Harvest estimates for lesser snow geese are available for the Skagit and Fraser river deltas from special state and provincial surveys, and for entire states and provinces from national surveys in the United States and Canada (Table 6). Prior to 1975, harvest estimates are available only from the Skagit River Delta since 1948 where an average of 5,941 snow geese were harvested annually (range = 720–10,920 geese). Lesser snow goose harvest on the Skagit and Fraser river deltas are assumed to be primarily from the Wrangel Island population, whereas snow goose harvest in California, Oregon, Washington, and British Columbia are assumed to be from the Wrangel Island and Western Arctic populations, and to a lesser extent from the Midcontinent population. Harvest estimates for the Skagit and Fraser river deltas have been relatively stable with apparent increases during the 1980s and 2000s for the Skagit River Delta. Harvest estimates for California have increased in association with the increase in lesser snow goose abundance in California when data are available (1999 to present). Trends in lesser snow goose harvest were not apparent in Oregon, Washington, and British Columbia during the same time period.

Acknowledgements

Many individuals participated in cooperative surveys over many years to monitor the status of Wrangel Island snow geese in Russia, Canada, and the United States and are too numerous to mention by name in this report. However, primary collaborators at the time of this report include Evgeny Syroechkovskiy (All Russian Research Institute for Nature and Conservation), Vasiliy Baranyuk (Working Group on Waterfowl of Northern Eurasia, NP RGG), Alexander Gruzdev (Wrangel Island Nature Reserve), Andre Breault and Sean Boyd (Canadian Wildlife Service), Don Kraege and Kyle Spragens (Washington Department of Fish and Wildlife), Brandon Reishus (Oregon Department of Fish and Wildlife), Melanie Weaver (California Department of Fish and Wildlife, and Todd Sanders (U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service).

Original data are available and maintained by each primary cooperator responsible for collecting the data. Additionally, band and recovery data are available from the U.S. Geological Survey's Bird Banding Laboratory. Personnel from the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service's Pacific Flyway Office maintain a copy of the summarized data provided by each cooperator, and a database for banding and band resight data. The collective data are intended to facilitate information exchange and cooperative management of Wrangel Island snow geese among the government agencies with jurisdiction in each country.

Table 1. Abundance and productivity of Wrangel Island snow geese on Wrangel Island, Russia, 1969–present.

Year	Abundance				Nest			Brood Size ²		Colony size (ha)
	Total	SY ¹ (%)	Adults	Breeding adults	Number	Succ. (%)	Clutch size	Colony	Rearing area	
1969				114,000	58,200		3.7			1,962
1970	150,000	20.0	120,000	120,000	60,000	96.0	3.7	3.5	2.5	2,600
1971	132,000	9.1	120,000	24,000	12,000	55.0	4.7	3.4	2.3	825
1972	107,000	0.6	106,000	36,000	18,000	45.0	4.2	3.5	2.3	950
1973	86,000	0.0	85,900	12,000	6,000	67.0	6.0	3.9		200
1974	70,000	0.7	69,500	32,000	15,000	0.0	4.7			800
1975	56,000	0.0	56,000	56,000	28,000	74.4	3.8	3.4	2.4	
1976	58,000	20.7	46,000	46,000	23,000	79.0	3.7	3.2	2.8	1,840
1977	68,200	16.1	57,200	10,000	5,000	76.8	5.0	3.7		400
1978	65,400	0.8	64,900	42,000	21,000	80.0	4.2	3.7	2.4	2,200
1979	84,500	26.5	62,100	60,000	30,000	90.0	3.8	3.6		1,860
1980	90,700	11.5	80,300	20,000	10,000	70.0	5.4	3.3		315
1981	89,000	3.2	86,200	78,000	39,000	95.0	4.0	3.7	3.1	2,118
1982	100,000	18.5	81,000	28,000	14,000	65.0	4.1	3.2	2.8	688
1983	95,000	2.4	92,800	3,400	1,700	5.9	4.8			125
1984	85,000	0.0	85,000	42,000	21,000	83.3	3.7	3.2	2.1	1,500
1985	85,000	5.4	80,000	50,000	25,000	87.7	3.7	3.2	2.4	1,457
1986	90,000	20.4	70,000	58,000	29,000	90.0	3.9	3.6	3.2	2,100
1987	100,000	15.0	85,000	47,000	23,500	80.0	3.7	3.4	2.8	1,900
1988	80,000	17.7	80,000	13,000	6,500	51.0	5.2	3.4	2.7	675
1989	70,000	1.4	70,000	60,000	30,000	60.0	3.8	3.3		1,025
1990	60,000	0.0	60,000	53,000	26,500	49.2	3.8	3.2	2.2	940
1991	60,000	6.6	56,000	41,600	20,800	82.0	4.1	3.4	2.7	888
1992	70,000	20.0	56,000	46,200	23,100	70.1	4.0	3.5	3.5	742
1993	65,000	0.8	64,500	52,200	26,100	85.1	3.9	3.2		910
1994	70,000	25.0	52,500	30,000	15,000	13.0	2.8	2.1		1,000
1995	65,000	0.8	64,000	8,800	4,400	50.0	4.7	2.8		430
1996	75,000	0.0	75,000	75,400	37,700	75.4		3.7	2.4	740
1997	85,000	15.0	70,000	55,200	22,600	71.2	4.0	3.5		628
1998	90,000	10.0	80,000	31,800	15,900	66.0	4.6	3.5		750
1999	90,000	5.6	85,000	20,800	10,400	75.0	4.7	3.3		278
2000	95,000	8.0	87,400	49,600	24,800	87.8	3.5	3.2	2.8	738
2001	105,000	12.0	92,400	48,000	24,000	87.0	3.6	3.2	2.3	900
2002	110,000			60,600	30,300	81.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	855
2003	115,000			55,000	27,500	77.5			2.2	900
2004	117,500	4.9	111,700	56,800	28,400	75.0	3.6	3.2		838
2005	117,500			95,800	47,900	82.3	4.2	3.7	3.3	900
2006	132,500	23.9	100,800	93,200	46,600	87.7	4.0	3.7	3.2	875
2007	140,000			79,000	39,500	84.4	4.0	3.5	3.1	1,100
2008	140,000			20,000	10,000	35.0				
2009	132,500			108,800	54,400	79.5	4.1	3.6		

Year	Abundance			Nest			Brood Size		Colony size (ha)
	Total	SY ¹ (%)	Adults	Breeding adults	Number	Succ. (%)	Clutch size	Colony Rearing area	
2010	150,000			10,000	5,000				
2011	155,000	5.0		144,000	72,000	81.0	4.2	3.7	
2012 ³									
2013	160,000				78,300	75.8	3.7	3.2	2.7
2014 ³									
2015	240,000	4.8	228,500	215,600	107,800	89.1	4.0	3.7	2,680
2016	300,000	20.0	251,000	236,000	118,000	89.5	3.9	3.7	3,240

¹ Second year (i.e., subadult) geese.

² Juveniles per adult nesting pair estimated at the colony post hatch and subsequently after birds moved to the rearing area.

³ No data available.

Table 2. Abundance of white geese (snow and Ross's geese) in California and on the Skagit and Fraser river deltas (Skagit-Fraser) near the border of Washington and British Columbia, 1948–present.

Year	Skagit-Fraser		California		Total
	Est.	Juv. (%)	Est.	Ross's (%)	
1948	26,000	16.3			
1949	29,400	10.4			
1950	18,160	4.1			
1951	16,075	24.1			
1952	25,700	14.8			
1953	17,230	13.4			
1954	22,558	9.9			
1955	19,091	4.6			
1956	15,100				
1957	20,373				
1958	26,986				
1959	14,246				
1960	24,425				
1961	22,180				
1962	27,641				
1963	23,600				
1964	21,800	15.8			
1965	26,100				
1966	15,800	31.1			
1967	17,800				
1968	22,600				
1969	15,400				
1970	31,676				
1971	35,968				
1972	23,800				
1973	18,980				
1974	12,450				
1975	12,346	33.2			
1976	16,017				
1977	24,904			34.1	
1978	16,075				
1979	35,600		492,500		528,100
1980	22,400	19.0	181,800		204,200
1981	48,600		711,300		759,900
1982	26,100	5.8	328,000		354,100
1983	24,500	0.0	523,100		547,600
1984	26,600	12.6	439,700		466,300
1985	46,200	24.0	503,600		549,800
1986	39,900	25.0	481,800		521,700
1987	47,700	30.0	477,600		525,300

Table 2. Continued.

Year	Skagit-Fraser		California		Total
	Est.	Juv. (%)	Est.	Ross's (%)	
1988	43,800	6.0	397,200		441,000
1989	32,200	0.0	431,700	41.9	463,900
1990	31,700	10.0	676,800	43.6	708,500
1991	39,100	28.0	651,000		690,100
1992	34,300	2.0	605,000	36.9	639,300
1993	49,100	40.0	520,100		569,200
1994	42,600	6.0	435,600		478,200
1995	37,000	5.0	464,400		501,400
1996	45,800	23.0	320,500		366,300
1997	47,000	13.0	369,400		416,400
1998	47,100	14.0	307,200		354,300
1999	28,600	15.6	550,400		579,000
2000	56,300	20.3	600,500	38.4	656,800
2001	52,000	21.1	396,200		448,200
2002	73,100	26.7	523,700		596,800
2003	66,800	12.8	521,000		587,800
2004	68,141	15.3	682,128		750,269
2005	80,040	35.9	630,686	34.8	710,726
2006	79,891	21.2	719,810		799,701
2007	94,859	21.8	978,622		1,073,481
2008	57,000	1.0	900,403	31.3	957,403
2009	73,964	40.0	827,055		901,019
2010	63,641	4.5	800,156		863,797
2011	69,964	20.6	1,027,887	25.6	1,097,851
2012	56,973	18.6	824,432		881,405
2013	75,313	22.4	1,275,890		1,351,203
2014	58,007	8.5	1,141,579	31.9	1,199,586
2015 ¹	66,501	26.2			

¹ No data available for California.

Table 3. Bandings, recaptures, resightings, and recoveries (shot or found dead) of Wrangel Island snow geese, 1988–present.

Year	Bandings ¹			Recaptures ¹	Resightings ²		Recoveries ³
	Leg	Neck	Tarsus		Neckband	Tarsusband	
1988	1,243						44
1989	460						45
1990	1						22
1991	121						17
1992	258			1			23
1993	796	543	253				56
1994	726	725	375		1,391	6	57
1995	1,923	499	233	9	4,083	6	68
1996	1,625	958		66	5,985	10	150
1997	1,752		593	46	7,543	17	138
1998	1,077	79		154	2,156	4	102
1999	999	176		273	211		118
2000	973	183	1	104	274		123
2001	1,326	247		164	377		109
2002	1,336			38	144		186
2003							146
2004	1,348			56	4		102
2005	1,156			67	35		177
2006	978				1		194
2007	1,017			55	3		263
2008	1,037			113			389
2009	998			5			273
2010	1,000						249
2011	960						200
2012							229
2013							158
2014							106
2015	1,000			10			143
2016	1,218	199		16			74
Total	25,328	3,609	1,455	1,177	22,207	43	3,961

¹ Bandings and recaptures on Wrangel Island, Russia.

² Resightings in western North America.

³ Recoveries in Russia, Canada, United States, and Mexico

Table 4. Recoveries (shot or found dead) of Wrangel Island snow geese leg banded on Wrangel Island, Russia, 1988–present.

Year	United States																					Subtotal		
	AK	AZ	AR	CA	CO	ID	IL	KS	KY	LA	MO	MT	NE	NV	NM	ND	OR	SD	TX	UT	WA		WY	
1988	2			12													8					17		39
1989	3			15													9					8		35
1990	1			11													3					4		19
1991				9													3					2		14
1992	3			8													3					6		20
1993	3			19											1		12					11		46
1994	2			21													7					8		38
1995	1			15								2					23					14		55
1996	1			44								3					56					24		128
1997	4			54						1							33					23		115
1998	1	1		48			1			1		2					10			1	13		78	
1999	4			44								1					26					21		96
2000	4			35			1					1					27					30		98
2001	10	1		36			2										20					23		92
2002	6			60			1										40					52		159
2003	6			37			1										27	1				47		119
2004	2			39								1		1		5				1	36		85	
2005	6			34	1	1						1	2			22					83		150	
2006	10		1	41						1						21					75		149	
2007	6		1	55	1							4				38			1		119		225	
2008	9			51								1			1	10	1				280		353	
2009	7	1		80								1			1	35	1			1	108		235	
2010	8		1	60			4					2				1	30		1	1	113		221	
2011	13			62			4					1	1			10	1			1	81		174	
2012	16			65	1	5						4				16				1	98		206	
2013	24			59	1	10	1	1				2				3			1		35	1	138	
2014	3			43			4						1			10					29		90	
2015	3			76	1	9						2				12					13		116	
2016	2			35		11										4	2	1	1		6		62	
Total	160	3	3	1,168	5	54	1	1	1	1	1	28	4	1	3	1	523	6	4	7	1,379	1	3,355	

Table 4. Continued.

Year	Canada							Subtotal	Mexico	Russia	Total
	AB	BC	NU	NT	ON	SK	YT				
1988	2	3						5			44
1989	2	8						10			45
1990		2		1				3			22
1991		2						2		1	17
1992		2		1				3			23
1993		9		1				10			56
1994	1	17				1		19			57
1995		8				4		12		1	68
1996		21		1				22			150
1997	6	16				1		23			138
1998	4	16				1	1	22		2	102
1999	2	19				1		22			118
2000	5	18						23		2	123
2001	4	10		2				16		1	109
2002	7	20						27			186
2003	1	23		1		1		26	1		146
2004	1	15		1				17			102
2005	1	22		1	1	1		26		1	177
2006	1	39		1		3		44		1	194
2007	8	28				2		38			263
2008	4	24	1			7		36			389
2009	8	23				7		38			273
2010	8	13		1		6		28			249
2011	4	14		2		4		24	2		200
2012	11	6				1		18	2	3	229
2013	9	7				2		18		2	158
2014	5	5		2		4		16			106
2015	21	5		1				27			143
2016	8	2		2				12			74
Total	123	397	1	18	1	46	1	587	5	14	3,961

Table 5. Recaptures of Wrangel Island (WIP) and Western Arctic (WAP) populations of lesser snow geese on Wrangel Island, Russia (WI) and the western Arctic of Canada (WA) by area of banding or recovery, 1988–present.

Year	Number WAP recaptured on WI by WAP banding area				Number WAP banded by banding area				Weighted WAP recaptures ¹ by banding area				Number WIP recaptured on WA by WIP recapture area				Number banded WIP	Weighted WIP recaptures ¹ by banding area			
	AK	NT	NU	Total	AK	NT	NU	Total	AK	NT	NU	Total	AK	NT	NU	Total		AK	NT	NU	Total
1988					640	1,733	58	2,431					0	0	0		1,243				
1989					436	1,043	2,967	4,446					0	0	0		460				
1990					1,208		3,578	4,786					0		0		1				
1991					17		4,422	4,439					0		0		121				
1992	0	0	0	0		1	3,553	3,554						0	0		258				
1993					1,207	2	4,234	5,443						0	0		796				
1994						388	4,736	5,124						0	0		726				
1995	0	0	0	0		1,928	5,343	7,271						0	0		1,923				
1996	0	1	0	1		1,652	6,632	8,284	1.2		1.2			0	0		1,625				
1997	0	0	0	0			11,660	11,660							0		1,752				
1998	0	0	0	0	1	1,081	14,629	15,711						0	0		1,077				
1999	0	1	0	1		1,735	10,609	12,344	1.2		1.2			0	0		999				
2000	0	0	0	0	227	2,460	15,953	18,640					0	3	0	3	973	2.6		2.6	
2001	0	0	0	0	307	2,542	15,796	18,645					0	0	0		1,326				
2002	0	1	0	1	821	1,359	15,452	17,632	0.6		0.6		0	0	0		1,336				
2003					1,075	1,343	16,666	19,084					1	0	0	1		0.7			0.7
2004	1	3	0	4	1	1,571	12,795	14,367	2.1	1.7		3.8	0	0	0		1,348				
2005	1	2	1	4	1,253	1,870	21,479	24,602	2.5	1.2	0.1	3.7	1	0	0	1	1,156	0.8		0.8	
2006					1,737	2,028	13,418	17,183					2	0	0	2	978	1.7		1.7	
2007	3	2	0	5	1,693	1,427	25,316	28,436	3.9	1.1		4.9	2	0	0	2	1,017	1.7		1.7	
2008	0	1	0	1	2,772		17,930	20,702					2		0	2	1,037	1.7		1.7	
2009	0	0	0	0	3		13,103	13,106					0		0	0	998				
2010					2,750		21,860	24,610					0		0	0	1,000				
2011					4,790		12,727	17,517					0		0	0	960				
2012					3,306	1	19,411	22,718					0	0	0	0					
2013					2,056		14,639	16,695					0		0	0					
2014					1,250		12,340	13,590					3		0	3		3.0			3.0
2015	0	1	0	1	3,502	1,477	17,810	22,789		1.4		1.4	0	0	0	0	1,000				
2016	2	2	0	4	1,860	2,465	8,824	13,149	0.8	2.7		3.5	0	0	0	0	1,218				
Total	7	14	1	22	32,912	28,106	347,940	408,958	2.3	1.4	0.1	3.7	11	3	0	14	25,328	1.6	2.6		4.2

¹ Number recaptured divided by 8-year moving average of number banded multiplied by 1,000.

Table 6. Harvest of lesser snow geese in the primary migratory and wintering areas of Wrangel Island snow geese in the United States and Canada from state and provincial harvest surveys on the Skagit and Fraser river deltas (local) and from national harvest surveys (State-Province), 1975–present.

Year	Local			State-Province				
	Fraser	Skagit	Total	BC	WA	OR	CA	Total
1975	2,972	2,880	5,852	2,625				
1976	1,102	5,064	6,166	2,131				
1977	576	1,680	2,256	508				
1978	401	3,420	3,821	394				
1979	1,917	6,372	8,289	1,944				
1980	1,725	4,908	6,633	1,628				
1981	3,378	18,240	21,618	3,055				
1982	2,666	2,664	5,330	1,896				
1983		3,648	3,648					
1984	2,700	5,352	8,052	2,704				
1985	3,972	11,232	15,204	3,907				
1986		3,528	3,528					
1987	2,329	2,964	5,293	2,122				
1988	1,556	2,860	4,416	1,657				
1989	926	300	1,226	917				
1990	748	300	1,048	141				
1991	1,642	1,692	3,334	2,642				
1992	1,246	1,060	2,306	447				
1993	2,232	2,231	4,463	2,094				
1994	1,838	1,294	3,132	2,137				
1995	746	584	1,330	1,589				
1996	1,869	2,184	4,053	2,863				
1997	1,536	1,598	3,134					
1998	1,351	1,163	2,514	1,797				
1999	1,426	1,781	3,207	1,990	2,686	4,462	41,145	50,283
2000	1,970	2,394	4,364	2,559	1,463	7,899	26,344	38,265
2001	1,468	1,744	3,212	2,354	3,574	6,283	33,860	46,071
2002	2,224	3,026	5,250	7,121	6,730	7,810	25,180	46,841
2003	2,387	2,849	5,236	1,257	2,641	5,186	33,037	42,121
2004	978	2,592	3,570	1,188	1,535	945	35,355	39,023
2005	4,223	8,150	12,373	2,443	10,713	2,877	46,934	62,967
2006	3,371	6,796	10,167	3,170	13,334	11,160	43,551	71,215
2007	4,782	18,828	23,610	4,626	22,501	9,021	52,038	88,186
2008	1,426	12,186	13,612	2,406	10,920	3,231	70,946	87,503
2009	4,568	15,535	20,103	1,316	14,102	4,218	30,693	50,329
2010	1,935	5,304	7,239	983	2,285	2,220	54,548	60,036
2011	3,990	13,204	17,194		11,563	4,088	43,718	59,369
2012	3,317	7,039	10,356	2,084	11,562	4,487	45,261	63,394
2013	3,607	6,865	10,472	1,208	4,383	2,409	38,747	46,747
2014	1,100	2,758	3,858	507	4,297	1,547	66,492	72,843
2015		3,446	3,446	613	4,471	2,029	51,947	59,060

